

The Impact of Cyberbully Assaults on Human Dignity: What Is to be Done?

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses the problem of cyberbullying, which has negative impact on the human dignity in general and the mental and physical health in particular of the survivors and victims of online attacks. The aim of the paper is threefold: 1) to investigate the characteristics of online violence, 2) to examine the consequences of Internet harassment on the survivors and victims, and 3) to provide a survey of the different measures that can be put to place to promote and protect the dignity and rights of everyone occupying the cyberspace. Integrative narrative literature review is the method used with which to comb through the scholarly and official government publications. The findings reveal the following. Digital violence comes in different forms. Survivors experience violations of their human dignity and different types of mental anguish. To the extreme, victims commit suicide. There are several measures that different institutions undertake both to prevent proactively and to counter retroactively digital violence.

Keywords: Cyberbullying, Digital Violence, Emotional Intelligence, Human Dignity and Rights, Mental Health

INTRODUCTION

Problem Statement

This paper addresses the current emerging problem according to which as social media grows in popularity, especially among the youth, more and more people are exposed to online harassment.

Research Questions

This paper raised the following queries:

1. What are the characteristics of digital violence?
2. What is its impact on human dignity?
3. What interventions can be undertaken to curb such online social aggression?

Purpose of the Research

Based on the foregoing, this paper sought to identify the features of Internet bullying, scrutinize the impact of digital harassment on the dignity of the addressee, and seek ways by which these acts of aggression can be curbed.

Contributions

The findings of this research shall benefit the survivors and victims of cyberbullying, as they will provide a glimpse of the general features of the acts of cyber harassment, an understanding of the impact of

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Bullying refers to individual's or individuals' intentional act of aggression against a person who cannot easily defend oneself, which is committed face-to-face (Krešić Ćorić & Kaštelan, 2020). With the introduction and use of the Internet en masse, bullying jumped from the real world to the digital world. Hence, by extension, cyberbullying refers to aggression perpetrated against someone or some ones through the Internet. Digital technology is relatively a new phenomenon, with it came digital bullying is also relatively new (Ong, 2017). Three factors define bullying: 1) intent, 2) repletion, and 3) imbalance of power (Englander, Donnerstein, Kowalski, Lin, & Parti, 2017). Some bully others for fun; while others, to commit intentional harm (Shariff & DeMartini, 2015). Bullies use psychological power over their targets who are powerless. Bullies gain the support of others, while targets are for the most part alone and helpless.

METHOD

A relatively new topic, cyberbullying refers to all kinds of negative behavior online, which this paper addresses. The subject cuts across different academic and professional disciplines. This paper is a critical survey of literature. It swept the academic journals, professional journals, as well as official government websites on the topic of digital violence, including psychiatry journals and

public health journals. A database search for literature was carried out in EBSCO, ERIC, JSTOR, ORCID, SCOPUS, and other related search engines to identify research published in the most recent years.

Key terms used for the search engines include cyberbullying, cyber-bullying, cyber harassment, cyber incivility, digital violence, electronic bullying, internet bullying, online bullying, online harassment, online aggression, online social aggression, and trolling. Data on cyberbullying were extracted from each literature. The titles and abstracts were screened for inclusion in or exclusion from the review, after which the full text was downloaded and reviewed, and a descriptive analysis was performed. The aim of the narrative literature review was to examine digital violence, its impact on human dignity, and the actions needed to prevent or counter cyberbullying.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Nature of Cyberbullying

This section responds to Research Question 1. Digital violence is a continuum, which scales from incivility and could lead to off-line real-world attacks, killings, and death. Here, I create a preliminary taxonomy of digital and offline cruelty that leads to death, at the extreme. See Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: From Digital Violence to Offline Deaths

Incivility and micro-aggression (Rini, 2020) could mean insensitivity or rudeness, which could be both witting or unwitting. Favoritism and stereotyping are forms of micro-aggression (Rini, 2021). These are in the lower stage of negative relationship with another person. An example of incivility, both digital or face-to-face, is for one person to respond in this way to another person who asks a question: “Just check Google” or “Why don’t you do your own research?” Bullying on the other hand is more intense. It includes name calling, insults, and attack on one’s character, bordering on infamy, libel, and defamation. Examples of bullying, both online and offline, include: “you’re dumb, stupid, a moron” and worse. You can imagine shoddier descriptions, denunciatory language, abusive expressions, and invectives. Online bullying can occur in different areas of cyberspace: chat rooms, message boards, online fora, online gaming communities, and social media (Affairs (ASPA), 2019c).

Cyber bullying has peculiar features, different from physical face-to-face bullying: it is 1) persistent, 2) permanent, and 3) difficult to be noted (Affairs (ASPA), 2019c). People look at their digital devices 24/7; hence, recipients of online harassment cannot escape the onslaught of attacks and seek solace. Whatever is posted online is oftentimes public and permanent, thus can impact on one’s reputation, which could adversely affect college admission and job opportunities. Parents,

teachers, and office colleagues might not notice or be aware that Internet violence has occurred; thus, no assistance, counseling, support, or stoppage of the act is forthcoming.

Studies reveal that bullies are the same people: they are bullies offline and they are bullies online (Englander et al., 2017). Those who are bullied offline are also mostly the ones bullied online (Bottino, Bottino, Regina, Correia, & Ribeiro, 2015). Nowadays, electronic bullying is frequent. A systematic review of two health-related databases indicated that online bullying happens from 6.5% to 35.4% (Bottino et al., 2015). In the U.S., for example, the National Center for Education Statistics and the Bureau of Justice jointly conducted the National Crime Victimization Survey which revealed the statistics according to which 22% of students from 12 to 18 years old in 2019 were bullied at school, whereas 16% of students from grades 9 to 12 were electronically bullying in 2018 (“COE - Bullying at School and Electronic Bullying,” 2021). A Centers for Disease Control study of youth risk behavior exposed the statistics according to which about 15.7% of high school students in the United States were bullied electronically in 2018 (“YRBSS | Youth Risk Behavior Surveillance System | Data | Adolescent and School Health | CDC,” 2020).

Using the school violence questionnaire and the emotional coefficient inventory, an empirical cross-sectional study composed of 309 secondary-level schools, aged 12 to 16, 54.1% of whom were female, exposed that there is a relationship between emotional intelligence and bullying, whether online or offline (Méndez, Jorquera, Ruiz-Esteban, Martínez-Ramón, & Fernández-Sogorb, 2019). Levels of adaptability, stress management, and interpersonal relationships affect the probability of violent behavior of online and offline bullying (Méndez et al., 2019).

Impact of Online Social Aggression

This section responds to Research Question 2. Cyberbullying affects everyone, but impacts young folks more than anyone else, as they are the ones perpetually hooked on to the Internet. As an assault on human dignity, cyberbullying has a negative impact on the mental health of survivors (Méndez et al., 2019). Survivors and victims of digital or real-world social cruelty are often also the survivors and victims of online social cruelty as well (Englander et al., 2017). By survivors we mean people who bear psychological shock but live on, whereas by victims we mean people who undergo psychological trauma and end up dead. Both face-to-face and online bullying have negative psychological effects. Some have or have developed “thick skin,” ignore these aggressions or become callous to these attacks. While others are more sensitive and vulnerable, hurting their egos and sense of self-worth. Sharing content which can be factual or false, both of which are harmful and damage the dignity of the recipient, some acts of which cross the line into illegal and criminal behavior (Affairs (ASPA), 2019c). Some of the effects of digital violence include 1) severe depression, 2) substance abuse, 3) ideation and suicide attempts, and 4) actual suicides (Bottino et al., 2015).

A Turkish study revealed that there is a high incidence of adolescent-aged youth using the Internet, while their parents are unaware of the occurrence of cyber harassment (Uludasdemir & Kucuk, 2019). of People on the receiving end of cyberbullying are too many to enumerate. They fall under the whole spectrum of humankind. Here, I provide a taxonomy composed of two general types of

bullying, perceived or real: they include 1) bullying against people at the margins and 2) bullying against the hegemonic dominant group. See Figure below:

On the one end are people who do not belong to the hegemonic dominant mainstream majority and do not fit the “norm.” Thus, most of the targets of cyberbullying belong to the non-dominant sex (in this case, non-male and non-cisgender), color, race, ethnicity, nationality (Balakrishnan, Khan, & Arabnia, 2020). They include the poor, ethnic minorities, linguistic minorities, cultural minorities, women, LGBTQIA+, people who are challenged in abilities, appearance, height, size, weight, wealth, and the like. In these cases, from my store of readings over the decades, we hear of ableism, ageism, anti-feminism, biphobia, Christian chauvinism, cis-normativity, cissexism, classism, colorism, discrimination, ethnocentrism, gender binarism, heterosexism, homophobia, institutionalized racism, Islamophobia, misogyny, racism, sexism, transphobia, U.S. chauvinism, and white supremacy. African Americans and their allies perceive “Black Lives Matter” as a positive slogan. Concrete examples of online harassment include posting non-consensually information, messages, photos, or videos, that are cruel, spiteful, disconcerting, hateful, or expose all kinds of personal data, which could be embarrassing or destructive of privacy (Affairs (ASPA), 2019a).

On the other end are people who belong to the hegemonic dominant mainstream majority and those who fit the “norm.” In the United States, for instance, conservative white males, mostly rural, feel threatened, rightly so or not. They perceive “White Lives Matter” as a positive slogan. They are defensive. They feel threatened. They feel attacked. They say they are made to feel “white guilt.” There are also conservative white females who also say they are made to feel “white guilt.” Thus, no one is immune to cyberbullying, whether real or perceived. They consider “critical race theory” as offensive. Here, we hear of anti-Semitism intentionally confused with anti-Zionism which are two very different matters, femi-fascism, gender policing, and the like. See Figure 2 below:

Figure 2: A Typology of Actual or Perceived Bullying against Different Segments in U.S. Society

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

Online harassment is an emerging reality with which individuals, families, schools, offices, communities, and even whole countries are confronted on a daily basis, as a result of human ocular omnipresence online, especially with mobile phones (Krešić Ćorić & Kaštelan, 2020). Digital violence takes shape in so many different forms. Its targets cuts across all political, cultural, and economic lines of humanity whose human dignity is bruised. However, there are steps that can be undertaken to prevent or remedy Internet violence.

Tasks Ahead

This section responds to Research Question 3. Linked to the introduction and massive use of the Internet through the desktop computers, laptop computers, tablets, and most especially, mobile phones, cyberbullying is a relatively new phenomenon. Hence, more studies need to be conducted for us to understand fully all its characteristics to date, the extent to which it is exercised, the extent to which it impacts people, and what could be done to prevent and stop cyberbullying. See Figure 3 below:

Figure 3: Ty Model of Digital Violence, Impact, and Interventions

In the U.S., evidence-based interventions on online harassment are still wanting (Lancaster, 2018). The growing phenomenon of digital violence is a wake-up call for all of us to take action at all levels: at home, in the schools, at the work place, and elsewhere, which need the intervention of family, friends, school authorities, social media help desks, counselors, psychotherapists, local authorities, and even local, national, or international law enforcement agents, when necessary. In the event that we learn of a critical event of cyberbullying happening, we must all jump into action as quick reaction, as we could save the mental health or even the life of a month.

There are several interventions that can be undertaken to prevent proactively and to halt retroactively cyberbullying, among which are the following. There are three major institutions of socialization, where cyberbullying can be prevented proactively: 1) the family, 2) schools, and 3) places of worship. An integral component of emotional intelligence, learning good manners and right conduct begins at home. For the child, parents and families are the first learning agents who

impart knowledge, values, and attitudes. The second institutions where children learn proper behavior, offline then and online as well today, are the schools, especially at the early stages of schooling. The third major institutions where people learn to be civil to one another are churches, mosques, synagogues, temples, and other related places of worship. Additionally, some civic organizations also impart such ideas, skills, and values of kindness and mutual respect include the Boy Scouts, Girl Scouts, Junior Jaycees, Rotary Ann Youth, Rotary Youth, and similar civic organizations. Human resource departments of companies as well as government agencies are slowly catching up with online harassment and hate crimes, for which reason they are coming up with guidelines with which Internet bullying must be dealt. See Figure 4 below:

Figure 4: Institutions of Socialization which Proactively Promote Civility, Offline and Online

At the middle school and high school levels, pupils can learn about good citizenship, which includes offline and online behavior, in civic education or citizenship education classes, which promote the respect of human dignity of everyone, locally and internationally. Parents and all those who supervise minors must adjust the “parental guidance settings” of all electronic devices as well as check the online status of the latter to ensure their safety in the ethernet all the time. They must be aware of the warning signs that a child is being digitally bullied or are digitally bullying others (Affairs (ASPA), 2019b).

Based on the known emotional intelligence factors of 1) adaptability, 2) stress management, and 3) interpersonal relationships as factors that are linked to online and offline behavior of bullying, school, office, and other authorities must put in place preventive measures for avoiding digital and real-world bullying (Méndez et al., 2019).

A new technique has been developed to measure cyber bullying. It is the online computerized adaptive testing (CAT), which can reveal bullying prevalence (Méndez et al., 2019). It uses a 22-item Negative Acts Questionnaire-Revised (NAQ-R). The results of the test reveal as high, moderate, or low level of bullying, after which a mental health professional comes to the service of the person bullied. If and when it will be further developed and made user friendly for people of all ages and walks of life, or if a similar test will be made available, it can be used to monitor incidence of cyber bullying as a way to deal with the matter thereafter.

There are tests that identify gendered or non-gendered aggression as well as identify language as not aggressive, covertly aggressive, or overtly aggressive (Safi Samghabadi et al., 2020). Through these tests, offensive language, aggression, or hate-speech could be detected. These types of tests could be widely used for spotting cyberbullying.

Retroactively, when online harassment takes place, some of the things that must be done include the following: 1) notice the emotions and behavior, 2) engage in a dialogue for fact finding 3) keep a record of the critical incidents, such as take screenshots, 4) report to school authorities or social media crisis or help desks, and 5) express concern to the survivor with the support of family, friends, and mental health professionals (Affairs (ASPA), 2019b). In the event that cyberbullying occurs, people affected need to inform someone on a running scale whom you trust about the incident, such as parents, teachers, adult siblings, adult friends, colleagues, and eventually to the authorities, especially if the cyberbullying will potentially lead to or have already led to physical violence.

As a response to bullying on the Internet, some social media outlets, such as Facebook, now have “civility clauses” that managers of groups and pages can post to their electronic walls, including removing and blocking people from participating or being members of these groups or pages. Other outlets, such as Twitter, bans and blocks people who tweet incendiary messages that lead people to acts of violence. Though reactive, these are necessary and important measures that giant social media outlets are putting to order.

Twitter, for example, already has an automatic cyberbullying detection program. It spots psychological traits of its users through machine learning (Balakrishnan et al., 2020). Four types of Twitter users are identified: normal, spammer, bully and aggressor (Balakrishnan et al., 2020). Thus, when cyberbullies are reported to Twitter, the company double checks on the psychological characteristics of the alleged online bully through machine learning and acts accordingly.

Digital violence can be nipped at the bud proactively, if all these institutions of socialization do their jobs and retroactively if schools, offices, social media outlets, and governments monitor violators of Internet civility clauses, including crossing over to criminal online behavior.

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